

Analysis of the Gender Perceptions of Generations X, Y, and Z through Advertisements¹

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Abstract

Gender perception, which is greatly affected by the socio-cultural characteristics of societies, varies from society to society. Gender perception is greatly influenced by the media's representations of men and women. Initiatives such as the Unstereotype Alliance Platform have increased the number of advertisements that seek to change gender perceptions. In this context, the problem of the study is to reveal the gender perception of generations X, Y and Z through 3 advertisements published in Turkey. Phenomenological design and maximum variation sampling were preferred in this study, which is an example of qualitative research. Within the scope of the study, advertisements of 3 brands that are members of the Unstereotype Alliance Platform were selected, and structured in-depth interview questions were prepared.

The selected commercials were shown to 24 people from generations X, Y, and Z. As a result of the study, most of the X, Y, and Z generations expressed a positive opinion about men and women doing housework together and they found the message given in the selected advertisements positive. In addition, participants requested advertisers to increase the number of advertisements showing men doing housework. It was emphasized that normalizing men's active role in housework could be a positive step towards gender equality.

Keywords: Gender, Stereotypes, Gender Roles, XYZ Generation, Advertisement.

JEL Codes: D83, L82, M37, Z10

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Introduction

Gender is a concept that describes the different attributes between women, men, girls, and boys and the social and cultural roles of these groups. While the patriarchal structure was more pronounced in the 1970s, since the 2000s, women's right to exist in every field has been emphasized, but the desired level of equality has not been achieved due to the persistence of the patriarchal mentality (Çık, 2017 & www.unicef.org, 2017). This situation leads to negative relationship outcomes for both men and women. Gender roles are also reflected in television advertisements and advertisements frequently use gender roles and stereotypes to reach large audiences and reinforce these stereotypes. The number of advertisements trying to change gender stereotypes has increased due to the influence of initiatives such as the "Unstereotype Alliance Platform" (Şener & Öztürk, 2022). It has been observed that studies examining the perspectives of viewers from different generations in advertisements prepared with this new approach are limited. The aim of this study is to examine the attitudes of generations X, Y, and Z in Turkey towards the division of domestic labor, to determine their perspectives in the context of gender, and to reveal their attitudes toward advertising campaigns that aim to transform gender stereotypes. Within the scope of the study, three advertisements from various product categories were selected and in-depth interviews were conducted with 24 participants belonging to generations X, Y, and Z. The results of this research are intended to provide guidance for advertisers that consider the power of advertisements to change society.

Literature Review

Gender, Stereotypes and Generation X, Y, and Z

Gender roles are social and behavioral norms accepted in society for individuals of a particular gender. They include traditional responsibilities assigned to women, men, girls and boys. These roles are shaped by local and global factors; including resource access, household structure, the global economy and ecological conditions (unicef.org, 2017). Zastrow & Kirst-Ashman (2016: 620-622) state that gender identity is an internal psychological concept and includes elements such as behavior and personality. Mead emphasizes that gender roles are highly variable in terms of physical environment, economic and political systems (Bates, 2013: 58; Schaefer, 2013: 276-277).

Gündüz-Kalan (2010: 79) states that women are often portrayed as caring, compassionate and maternal, while men are portrayed as strong, independent and less compassionate, and that these expressions are examples of gender stereotypes. Although it varies from one society to another, it is emphasized that

in many societies women are generally engaged in domestic work, while men undertake tasks outside the home (Marshall, 1999: 101).

Ann Oakley (1972), one of the pioneers of gender in social sciences, states that gender encompasses biological sex differences as well as the roles of masculinity and femininity defined by society. Oakley explains the interactions between men and women largely on the basis of biological differences. Simone de Beauvoir's "Le Deuxième Sexe" is a turning point in feminist literature. De Beauvoir analyzes how women have been constructed as the "other" throughout history and distinguishes between biological sex and gender. According to her, being a woman is not an innate characteristic, but a process of historical and social construction. Her most famous quote "One is not born a woman, one becomes a woman" summarizes this idea (Beauvoir, 2019: 26). Judith Butler, in her book "Gender Trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity" argues that gender is performative. According to her, gender is an identity that people create by constantly repeating certain behaviors. Butler argues that gender is not fixed and unchangeable, but is constantly reproduced according to social and cultural conditions. These ideas contributed to the development of queer theory (Butler, 2014: 16-17). Sandra Bem, on the other hand, has made a significant contribution to the field of psychology and gender studies with her work on gender. One of Bem's most well-known theories is the gender schema theory she developed in the 1970s. This theory argues that people learn and internalize gender roles according to social and cultural norms from an early age. Bem examines how gender roles shape individuals' perceptions and the role they play in adapting to social expectations (Bem, 1981: 354). According to Eagly and Wood (2016: 459), gender role beliefs arise from the observation of male and female behavior and lead to the inference that the sexes have certain characteristics that are appropriate for gender-specific roles. These characteristics are reflected in widely shared beliefs or gender stereotypes. Because these roles seem to reflect the inherent characteristics of the sexes, they are perceived as natural and inevitable.

Many studies have been conducted in the academic field to reveal the gender perspectives of women and men. In a study, it was determined that women's gender perception was higher than men's among participants at a state university (Alabaş et al., 2019). In gender stereotypes, being married or single can also be a determinant in gender stereotypes. Another study revealed that the gender perception of early married women is biologically and socially shaped (Tuna-Uysal et al., 2019). In a study conducted with men who stayed at home during the Covid-19 pandemic, it was stated that fathers who tried to participate equally were sensitive to gender equality, but experienced conflicts related to the-

ir father and masculinity roles (Kaya & Yaşar, 2021). In a similar study, it was revealed that women had a more egalitarian and positive gender perception than men, married and single women had similar attitudes, but single women had a more positive perception (Yılmaz et al., 2022). Another study revealed that married women exhibit more traditional gender attitudes as they get older (Altun, 2019). Intergenerational differences can also be effective in gender stereotypes. In a study conducted with high school students (Generation Y), it was found that some students were under the influence of traditional values on traditional gender role issues (Budak & Küçükşen, 2018). In a similar study, the attitudes of Generations X, Y and Z on gender equality were examined and it was found that Generation X had more traditional views than other generations (Akgül, 2022). In another study It was concluded that married women between the ages of 25-40 (Generation Y) have more egalitarian social attitudes than women between the ages of 40-55 (Generation X) (Paçacıoğlu, 2018). The views of individuals from different generations on gender in advertisements were examined and it was determined that Generation Y had a more critical and egalitarian perspective than other generations (Öztürk, 2020).

Gender and Advertising

The roles of men and women in society are also reflected in advertisements. Advertisements reinforce gender stereotypes by repeating coded images. Advertisements act in accordance with gender roles in the selection of characters (Gündüz-Kalan, 2010: 81; Meral, 2008: 20). While reproducing male and female roles, advertisements also normalize inequalities between men and women through gender stories (Nas, 2015: 13). Sancar (2009: 175) and Özdemir (2010: 103-104) state that women usually take part in advertisements for products related to housework, while men are depicted in scenes involving struggle and heroism outside the home. Gündüz-Kalan (2010: 79) states that women are often portrayed as caring, compassionate and maternal, while men are portrayed as strong, independent and less compassionate. It has been found that women in traditional roles in television advertisements are generally portrayed as good wives, mothers and housewives, women in decorative roles are presented as sexual objects, and even strong women are shown as lonely and unhappy (Aydın & Aslaner, 2015). In a study analyzing 489 television advertisements that won awards in the Effie Competition in the 2007-2018 period, it was determined that the main characters were mostly male and 89% of the voiceovers were performed by men. Women, on the other hand, were shown in the home environment and very rarely in the work environment (Şener & Öztürk, 2018). In a study conducted by the same academics, the rate of female voiceover was

found to be 38%, the rate of female main character was found to be 43%, and it was determined that the rate of female main character increased by around 40% in bank and finance sector advertisements (Şener & Öztürk, 2022). In an analysis of Ikea's advertisements broadcast in Sweden and Turkey, it was determined that in Sweden the female figure was shown as a prominent and prominent character, while in Turkey she was depicted as an auxiliary and obscure character (Kaya, 2017). In the March 8 International Women's Day advertisements, it was observed that women were depicted by going beyond traditional gender roles (Çilingir, 2019). Beko and Dove advertisements attracted attention with themes emphasizing gender equality (Çiftçi & Serçelik, 2021). In a study analyzing jewelry advertisements, it was found that the happiness of owning the product was shaped by gender norms and stereotypes (Terek Ünal & Kalan, 2022). It has been determined that male and female roles in television advertisements are shaped according to gender stereotypes (Yalman & Güdekli, 2018; Hülür & Kalafat Çat, 2018; Matthes et al., 2016). Studies conducted in men's magazines at different times have revealed that men are associated with concepts such as charismatic, stylish, luxurious, polite, confident, arrogant, narcissistic (Zengin, 2019; Kılınç, 2015; Hacısoftaoğlu & Elmas, 2015).

Unlike Turkey, academic studies revealing gender stereotypes in many advertisements have been conducted abroad. In a study examining 311 advertisements on Youtube, it was determined that gender stereotypes in advertisements were generally based on physical characteristics (Roth-Cohen et al., 2023). The study on the portrayal of gender roles in television advertisements in Asian, American and European countries clearly shows that gender stereotypes in TV advertisements can be found all over the world, regardless of a particular gender equality status in a particular country (Matthes et al., 2016: 314). In a study on the representation of gender in South African television advertisements, it was found that men are represented in advertisements as dominant in public work spaces and in positions of social authority, while women are represented as subordinate and subordinate in private-domestic spaces, in positions of social subordination, and this subordination implies their sexualization (Luyt, 2011: 356). In the study conducted to examine gender images and the formation of stereotypes in modern advertising practice, a sample analysis of magazine advertisements published in Russian language in magazines of different countries was carried out, and it was found that men in advertisements are portrayed as successful businessmen, politicians, artists and art people who pay attention to their appearance (Naisbayeva et al., 2018: 118). In the study examining advertisements published in Ukraine, it was found that women were depicted in stereotypical roles such as sex objects or housewives and limited to traditional gender roles,

while men were shown in more active and successful roles (Ostapchuk et al., 2024). Television advertisements in Brazil, Canada, China, Germany, South Korea, Thailand and the United States were analyzed, and it was found that men were featured in visual and auditory roles, while women were depicted in stereotypical ways (Paek et al., 2010: 192). In Ukraine, 200 advertisements broadcast on television channels were analyzed, and as a result of the research, it was determined that women were mostly portrayed as housewives, nurses, protectors, and maids in advertisements (Kitsa & Mudra, 2020: 381). In a study investigating the representation of women in advertising in Brazil, it was found that women of color, fat women and women over 40 were underrepresented in advertising (Shinoda et al., 2020: 629). An analysis of advertisements aired on Belgian television in 2002 and 2003 and in 2009 and 2010 found that there was little change in gender role portrayals between these years and that gender stereotypes in advertising persisted despite social and regulatory changes (Verhellen et al., 2014: 170). An analysis of financial advertisements published in *The Economist Magazine* over the last 70 years showed that 84% of the advertisements featured a man as the central figure, while women were often portrayed in subordinate roles and with limited knowledge of financial products (Unda & Niessen-Ruenzi, 2024).

Although gender role stereotyping in advertisements continues, it is stated that there has been a change in this issue over the years (Eisend et al., 2019). It is possible to state that there has been a slight improvement in this regard. The ads that won awards at the Crystal Apple Advertising Creativity Competition were analyzed and it was determined that they mostly reflect traditional gender roles, but there are some progressive roles (Sanay & Şener, 2021). In a study conducted on 8 advertisements shot between 2020 and 2023, it was determined that the advertisements broke down the social assumptions on the roles of men and women and treated the man as an individual who takes care of his child and home (Doğan & Kahraman, 2023). In a similar study, it was determined that there have been positive developments towards women's roles in advertisements, but female role stereotypes are still present and various roles with family roles have emerged in male depictions (Tsichla, 2020: 28). In the study on advertisements, it was determined that consumers reacted positively to the "Biscolata Man" advertisement and especially women preferred this image to the portrayal of the female body for sexual attraction (Ergin et al., 2018). In the study examining the gender stereotypes of award-winning digital video ads, it was found that women and men were portrayed equally in non-stereotypical activities and roles. However, the study reveals that central figures are more likely to be male than female, indicating a gender difference in terms of the identification of main roles (Aramendia-Muneta et al., 2019: 403).

Unstereotype Alliance Platform

In 2017, Unilever and UN Women (United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women) announced their cooperation and announced that they would work together to combat sexist stereotypes. Within the scope of this project, it was decided to work towards eliminating sexist judgments and representations in advertisements and media. Again at the Cannes Lions International Festival of Creativity in 2017, important organizations such as UN Women and the World Federation of Advertisers (WFA) announced the formation of the Unstereotype Alliance Platform. The platform was established to continue its activities as an idea and action platform aiming to create a more egalitarian and just world by supporting positive gender roles in media and advertising content (unstereotypealliance.org). The Unstereotype Alliance, which includes 12 countries and a total of 240 organizations, including Turkey as of 2019, is one of the largest global initiatives. The Unstereotype Alliance Turkey platform is the second national platform in the world. Major advertising professional organizations established in Turkey, particularly the Advertisers Association, and major advertisers operating in Turkey support the Unstereotype Alliance Platform. The lack of preference for women as an external voice in advertising, age discrimination, discrimination based on body size, men and women being stuck in traditional roles, and the existence of product categories where women are still underrepresented are among the issues that platform members emphasize (rvd.org.tr).

Parmelee and Codd (2023) draw attention to some issues in the "introduction" of the report "Women in Business-2023 Global Outlook" published by Deloitte. According to this report, housework often remains a burden on women and women often feel that they have to prioritize their partner's career. Although the majority of respondents work full-time, it is women who undertake the majority of household chores, with only a small proportion of them indicating that this responsibility lies with their partners. A significant proportion of women with lower incomes than their husbands feel that they should put their husbands' careers ahead of their own. In addition, it is observed that women view flexible working hours positively, but think that this may put them at a disadvantage. It has been revealed that advertisements that show women as strong and emphasize gender equality are more accepted and that such advertisements are more effective (Başfıncı et al., 2018).

Methodology

Aim of the Study

This study aims to examine advertising campaigns designed to alter the social perceptions of Generati-

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ons X, Y, and Z in Turkey. Although there are enough studies on women in the context of gender, there is insufficient research on men. With the impact of the Unstereotype Alliance Platform, the number of advertisements trying to change gender perceptions has increased. However, studies examining the perspectives of viewers from different generations on these advertisements are limited. The lack of research on this type of advertising perception in Turkey makes this study unique. The results of this research are intended to provide guidance for advertisers.

Methodology of the Study

The study was conducted using the in-depth interview technique from qualitative methods. Qualitative research offers the opportunity to analyze the study in detail (İslamoğlu & Alnıaçık, 2014: 221). Qualitative research is conducted when a problem or issue needs to be explored (Creswell, 2015: 47-48). Qualitative research is a process that examines perceptions and events in their natural environment holistically and realistically through methods such as observation, interview, and document analysis. By providing flexibility to the researcher, it allows the researcher to develop new methods and approaches in the research process (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011: 39-52). In the qualitative part of the study, phenomenological design and maximum variation sampling were preferred. By using maximum variation sampling, researchers can identify the main features and variable characteristics of a phenomenon experienced by different subgroups in a variety of contexts and thus synthesize studies that differ in various dimensions to create a holistic understanding of the phenomenon (Suri, 2011: 67-68).

Sample of the Study

Due to the purpose and subject of the research, this research requires a subject group to watch advertisements. Therefore, a quasi-experimental research was designed. This made it inevitable to work with young subjects (Generations X, Y, Z) due to their susceptibility to technology. However, this is an important factor limiting the generalizability of the research results. The findings are mostly valid for the young consumer segment. Participants under the age of 18 in Generation Z, which includes those born in 2000 and later, and members of Generation Alpha, which includes those born in 2010 and later, were excluded due to possible problems in obtaining parental leave under pandemic conditions. Generation Z was limited to those born in 2004 who were 18 years old at the time of the study. In terms of representing all three generations, the population of the study consists of individuals born between 1965 and 2004, aged 18 and over. The sample included 24 participants belonging to Generations X, Y and Z living in seven geographical regions of Turkey and living in

different cultural environments. Structured in-depth interviews were conducted face-to-face and online. Structured questions were created to measure the gender perceptions of Generations X, Y, and Z regarding advertising. The study adapted into Turkish by Uçar (2017: 92-93) and the study conducted by Gülmez (2017: 182) were utilized in formulating the questions. The prepared questions were checked and finalized by two academicians who are experts in their fields. After the questions were prepared, a pre-test was conducted and it was checked whether they were suitable for the study. In order to represent all three generations, the study was limited to individuals born between 1965 and 2004 and aged 18 and over. The sample includes 24 participants belonging to Generations X, Y and Z living in seven geographical regions of Turkey and living in different cultural environments. In the study, display advertisements published by advertisers who are members of the Unstereotype Alliance Platform were preferred. In the advertisements created in line with the objectives of the platform in question, the fight against the harmful attitude against women in the division of domestic labor and in the choice of profession and career is at the forefront. For this reason, advertisements in which the issue of domestic division of labor was covered were preferred for the study. The generations of the characters in the advertisements were also taken into consideration in the selection of advertisements. The in-depth interviews were conducted in the natural environment of the participants and with their voluntary participation. It was evaluated by the Uşak University Social Sciences and Humanities Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee at the meeting dated 13.01.2022 and as a result of the evaluation, it was decided that the methods to be applied within the scope of the research were ethically appropriate. In the study, the participants were interviewed between April 01 and May 31, 2022. Maximum diversity sampling was preferred in the study.

In the study, 10 display ads were selected by scanning the YouTube channels of advertisers. The selected advertisements were reduced to 3 by having the academic and administrative staff working at Uşak University Vocational School of Social Sciences and 2nd-year students of the Department of Radio and Television Programming watch them following the purpose of the study. In the research, "Erase with a single Solo" (Eczacıbaşı Holding brand) for Generation X, "Arçelik Imperium Go I is the most perfect version of a vacuum cleaner" (Arçelik-Koç Holding brand) for Generation Y, and "Fairy Platinum Plus is number 1 in tough food stains" (Fairy-P&G brand) for Generation Z were selected as advertisements reflecting gender. The content of the 3 advertisements shown to Generation X, Y, and Z respectively is given below.

Figure 1. Solo Disposable Cleaning Cloth Advertisement

The advertisement takes place in the kitchen of a house. A middle-aged woman and a man are cooking in the kitchen. They both enjoy their cooking. When the woman breaks the egg, some of it overflows onto the stove and contaminates it. While the man is cooking something in another pan, one of the ingredients overflows out of the pan and contaminates the stove. At the same time, milk boiling on the stove overflows and contaminates the stove. The male actor takes out a disposable Solo cleaning cloth and cleans the stove and countertop. Both actors are seen with a happy and proud expression.

Figure 2. Arçelik Imperium Go Vacuum Cleaner Advertisement

In the advertisement, a middle-aged man and woman are seen in the living room of a house. The female character sits on the sofa looking at her computer while the male character vacuums the house with a corded vacuum cleaner; he has difficulties with the cable and the hose. The vacuum cleaner's cord breaks down and the vacuum cleaner turns into a cordless vacuum cleaner. The wireless vacuum cleaner makes the male actor happy and he continues vacuuming with this new vacuum cleaner. Meanwhile, the different usage characteristics of the vacuum cleaner are shown. After the vacuuming is completed, the male character places the vacuum cleaner on the wall hanger, goes to the woman and they chat happily on the sofa.

Figure 3. Fairy Platinum Plus Dishwashing Detergent Advertisement

In the advertisement, two different families are shown. On the left side, in a blue-colored kitchen, there is the "Uğraşangiller" (Struggling Family) family consisting of a middle-aged mother and father and a boy around 10 years old. On the right side, in a green kitchen, is the "Pratikgiller" (Practical Family) consisting of a middle-aged mother and father, a girl around 13 years old, and a baby boy. The "Uğraşangiller" family scrubs the dishes thoroughly before placing them in the machine. The "Pratikgiller" family puts the dishes directly into the machine. The "Uğraşangiller" mother gives the "Pratikgiller" mother very dirty dishes and these dirty dishes are placed in the machine as it is. They come out of the dishwasher spotless. In the meantime, it is shown how the machine works. At the end of the wash, the "Pratikgiller" family happily puts away the clean dishes. The mother of the "Uğraşangiller" admires the cleanliness. In the end, it is emphasized that Fairy is the number one in tough food stains.

Research Questions

Structured questions were created in order to measure the gender perceptions of Generation X, Y and Z about advertising. While creating the questions, the study adapted into Turkish by Uçar (2017: 92-93) and the study conducted by Gülmez (2017: 182) were utilized. The prepared questions were checked by two academicians who are experts in their fields. Finally, a pre-test was conducted and the suitability of the questions for the study was checked. The study was limited to individuals born between 1965 and 2004 and aged 18 and over in order to represent all three generations. The interviews were conducted in the participants' natural environments and with voluntary participation.

The research questions of the study were formed as follows:

- What are the attitudes of male and female

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participants of Generation X, Y, Z towards advertisements that combat gender stereotypes?

- How male and female participants from Generation X, Y and Z evaluated the advertisement they watched according to the following statements:

Convincing, impressive, interesting, informative, understandable, attention grabbing, message relevance, likability, the persuasiveness of the male character's message, the persuasiveness of the female character's message, pleasant elements, unpleasant elements.

Collection and Processing of Research Data

The research questions were directed to the relevant sample group and their responses were obtained. The in-depth interview lasted 30 minutes for each person. Records were taken during the interview and then analyzed. The data obtained were categorized and analyzed. Men belonging to Generation X were coded as XE, women belonging to Generation X were coded as XK, men belonging to Generation Y were coded as YE, women belonging to Generation Y were coded as YK, men belonging to Generation Z were coded as ZE and women belonging to Generation Z were coded as ZK. (In Turkish, the word

for male starts with the letter E and the word for female starts with the letter K). For example, the 1st female participant from Generation X was coded as XK1 and the 3rd male participant from Generation Z was coded as ZE3).

Results

Within the scope of the research, the age range of the participants is between 18-53. 13 women and 11 men. Generation X is represented by 9 people (5 women and 4 men), Generation Y by 7 people (3 women and 4 men) and Generation Z by 8 people (4 women and 4 men). 12 of the participants are single and 12 are married. Two of the participants graduated from primary school, 1 from middle school, 10 from high school, 3 from associate's degree, 7 from undergraduate degree and 1 from postgraduate degree. Among these graduates, there are some who are continuing their education and the study is based on the most recent level of education. One of the participants is not employed. Among the employed participants, 8 work in the private sector, 4 in the public sector and 3 are self-employed. Again, 4 of the participants stated that they were university students.

Table 1. Generation X's Views on Advertising

Advertising Elements	XK1	XK2	XK3	XK4	XK5	XE1	XE2	XE3	XE4
Convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing
Impressive	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing
Interesting	Interesting	Interesting	Not Interesting	Not Interesting	Interesting	Not Interesting	Interesting	Not Interesting	Not Interesting
Informative	Not Informative	Informative	Informative	Informative	Informative	Not Informative	Informative	Not Informative	Not Informative
Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable
Attention Grabbing	Not Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing	Not Attention Grabbing	Not Attention Grabbing	Not Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing	Not Attention Grabbing	Not Attention Grabbing

Message Relevance	Not suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Not suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Not suitable	Suitable
Likability	Liked	Not Liked	Partially liked	Liked	Liked	Liked	Liked	Not Liked	Liked
The persuasiveness of the male character's message	Not convincing	Not convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Not convincing	Convincing
The persuasiveness of the female character's message	Convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Not convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Not convincing	Convincing
Pleasant elements	Cleanliness in the Kitchen	Cleanliness in the Kitchen	Family in the kitchen	Man in the kitchen	Cleanliness in the Kitchen	Man in the kitchen	Cleanliness in the Kitchen	Man in the kitchen	A happy family atmosphere
Unpleasant elements	There is nothing unpleasant	It is unrealistic to clean the kitchen so quickly	Exaggerated dirtiness	Exaggerated dirtiness	There is nothing unpleasant	There is nothing unpleasant	Exaggerated dirtiness	Exaggerated dirtiness	There is nothing unpleasant

The views of women in Generation X are summarized below:

Generation X women generally found the advertisement unconvincing and described the male and female characters as incompetent. "Milk overflowing is something I can't stand at all, it is very difficult to clean the milk stain from the stove, I was very uncomfortable with this, the reason for my discomfort is that a small napkin cannot clean that milk flow or egg white, they have heavy odors, hardened stains, so I was uncomfortable. Milk overflows when they are on the stove, they don't realize it, it was uncomfortable for me to be honest (XK3)", "It was not convincing. I think a Turkish woman cannot break eggs that dirty. It was not very convincing, I think it was very contrived, very contrived (XK4)". Female participants especially criticized the fact that a woman was so incompetent and found the way of cooking by dirtying the stove in the advertisement exaggerated. No. I didn't find it convincing, I mean, I think it's ridiculous. The food cooked at home is exaggerated. No, I think it is ridiculous to break an egg on the edge of the pan and pour it all over the stove (XK4)". Female participants pointed out that a small piece of cloth cannot be an alternative to the traditional cleaning with detergent and water, but they still stated that the product could be given a try due to its practicality. Female participants also found the description of the product's functions and features adequate, but the majority did not find the produ-

ct's claim of cleanliness realistic. "To be honest, the advertisement didn't convince me that a small napkin could clean so well, but visually it's a nice movie (XK3)". The fact that husband and wife work together in the kitchen was emphasized by the female participants. "I think this advertisement would have caught my attention. The fact that he was in the kitchen with his wife, that they were working together, preparing food, cleaning, working together, attracted my attention (XK3)", "I liked the fact that a man spent time in the kitchen, spent time with his wife. Because in our society, fathers are more distant from the kitchen. I don't know, all the burden falls on the mothers in the family. We like seeing fathers in the kitchen more recently than the old generation. This is important to lighten the burden of women (XK4)". Some of the female participants complained about the excessive workload at home. "I am a housewife, obviously I do all kinds of housework very, very much (XK2)". Participants who stated that fathers being more involved in the kitchen would lighten the burden of women stated that advertisements in which men and women are seen doing work together would set an example. "Yes, it is convincing. I think the message there is not just the feature of a wet wipe or a cleaning wipe. It also tells about a family cooking together in the kitchen, it also tells about being happy in the kitchen. It also tells that men should help their wives in the kitchen properly (XK4)". 1 participant stated that she would like to

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see women doing different jobs in advertisements rather than cleaning. "Actually, it would be better if we saw our women in other achievements rather than cleaning, but it was still convincing (XK2)". The female participants belonging to Generation X stated that they mostly did cooking, laundry and dishwashing, vacuuming and dusting at home, and emphasized that they actually undertook almost all household chores except for wiping windows. One participant expressed her desire to retire from housework by stating that she also does all the repair work at home. "If you ask me, I do all the housework at home. I do all the repair work. I do all the cleaning work. They all look after me. I want to retire. I mostly do vacuuming, mopping, and folding and collecting laundry (XK4)".

The views of men in Generation X are summarized below:

Generation X men generally found the advertisement unconvincing and described the male and female protagonists as incompetent. In particular, they criticized the fact that a man was so incompetent and found the way of cooking by dirtying the stove in the advertisement exaggerated. "I didn't like it because they are trying to create a perception that men are untalented and incompetent in the kitchen. Therefore, this is not realistic. Both men and women can be skilled in what they do, and both men and women can be incompetent in what they do (XE3)", "I like the feeling of cleanliness. What I don't like is that not many people spill and scatter at home like this. It seemed a bit exaggerated to me (XE2)". Male participants, like female participants, pointed out that a small piece of cloth cannot be an alternative to traditional cleaning work with detergent water and a cleaning cloth. "The message can vary depending on the age group. People my age might like this ad because it's partly about product use. People older than me would definitely object to it because they use washcloths. Young people would definitely use this product. Therefore, it is likely that it gave a different message to each age group (XE2)", "I don't think it is appropriate, no one would clean the stove with such a cloth. At least I wouldn't do it (XE3). The majority of the participants found the description of the product's functions and features simple, clear, and understandable. "I found the advertisement to

be understandable. It was short and concise for a 15-20 second advertisement, and they showed how easy the product was to clean. (XE1)", "I found it understandable, simple and plain (XE4)". The fact that the husband and wife work together in the kitchen and that the male character does the cleaning after cooking the food is a particular point emphasized by the participants. "The message given was appropriate. There were two messages; the first was how well he cleaned the kitchen, and the second was the presence of a man in the kitchen. Another issue could be that the kitchen is not shown as only a woman's job (XE1)", "The message given by the man is convincing. Because they also explained that it is not only a woman's job in the kitchen. The two of them gave a nice message together in the kitchen. But I couldn't remember the female actor. The male character played his role well in the advertisement. He played a person who helps his wife. The advertisement achieved its goal (XE2)". Participants stated that they play an active role in maintaining order and cleanliness in their homes, but emphasized that they do little cooking. "I do jobs such as emptying the dishwasher, ironing, collecting and throwing away garbage, and getting bottled water (XE4)", "I do all the housework in the house where I live, as a former tourism employee, I am proficient in all subjects except cooking (XE1)". While one participant found the picture of partners cooking together "fun", another participant described it as a "happy family picture". "The male character's acting is nice, but I laughed a lot when he did the cleaning (XE1)", "It's impressive because there's a nice kitchen and smiling people. There's a happy family atmosphere (XE4)". From the general statements of the participants, it can be said that they care about cleanliness and do not like dirty environments. "I don't like milk to boil over. When I break an egg, I don't break it on the side. I take it over the sink. I never break it on the stove so the stove doesn't get dirty. They should have been careful. They went a little overboard. Irregular life. It is not suitable for my lifestyle due to my age (XE2)", "I don't like something like that to spill in my house, I don't like it very much. There is a situation related to the promotion of the product, there are things done to show the attractiveness of the product etc., okay but this way of doing things bothered me a little (XE3)".

Table 2. Generation Y's Views on Advertising

Advertising Elements	YK1	YK2	YK3	YK4	YE1	YE2	YE3
Convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Convincing
Impressive	Impressive	Impressive	Impressive	Not Impressive	Impressive	Impressive	Impressive

Interesting	Interesting	Interesting	Interesting	Not Interesting	Interesting	Interesting	Interesting
Informative	Informative	Informative	Not Informative	Not Informative	Not Informative	Not Informative	Informative
Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Not Understandable	Not Understandable	Understandable	Understandable
Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing	Not Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing
Message Relevance	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Not Suitable	Not Suitable	Suitable
Likability	Liked	Liked	Liked	Not Liked	Partially liked	Partially liked	Partially liked
The persuasiveness of the male character's message	Convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing
The persuasiveness of the female character's message	Convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Not convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing
Pleasant elements	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant	Partially Pleasant	Partially Pleasant	Partially Pleasant	Partially Pleasant
Unpleasant elements	Exaggerated dirtiness	Nothing unpleasant	Nothing unpleasant	Nothing unpleasant	Nothing unpleasant	Partially unpleasant situation	Partially unpleasant situation

The views of women in the Y generation are summarized below:

Generation Y women generally find the advertisement impressive and convincing; they focus mostly on the transformation of the product from wired to wireless. "Yes, I found it interesting. Because according to my experience, the broom seems to be more convenient to use and sweeps more easily. I also liked the change (YK2)." The effects used in the animation sections of the advertisement were appreciated and it was seen that these effects helped the product achieve its informative goal. "It was told fantastically, like surreal events. That change, that innovation was actually interesting, we can say it was remarkable (YK1)", "Yes, it was remarkable. Effects such as the vacuum cleaner getting rid of its bulkiness, the plug coming out of the socket and changing shape were remarkable (YK1)". The majority of the participants found the description of the product's functions and features sufficient and focused on the different attachments. "I liked it, the ad explained the general features of the product well. The ad shows that it reaches places that are normally hard to reach by vacuuming. It shows that it does this by using light and in a way that you can easily see. It shows that the broom can reach different places like the bookshelf. They put a cat, it probably has a feature related to hair. It explains such features, I liked it because it shows how it makes life easier (YK3)".

According to some participants, the fact that the male actor " helps" his wife in the cleaning work and " undertakes a task" in this regard is a matter that the participants especially emphasized. "I generally liked the advertisement I watched. It was nice that the couples helped each other and introduced the vacuum cleaner. (YK2)", "I think the male character in the advertisement was positioned very well. Because housework is not only specific to women, or it is not something that belongs to a single gender. The male character is united with a female figure there, but this may not be the case in real life, men can live alone and do such work alone. This is not something that is attributed only to the female gender or the concept of woman. Here, I think the brand has drawn attention to this, which is very nice and appropriate (YK1)". One participant stated that at the beginning of the advertisement when the woman was sitting, she assumed that the man was unhappy because he was uncomfortable doing this job, but then she realized that his unhappiness was due to the problem he had with the cable. The same participant pointed out that the woman can use the time she spends vacuuming the house more efficiently while her husband does this job. Participants pointed out that housework should not be perceived as something that belongs only to women, and emphasized the importance of cooperation between spouses, as depicted in the advertisement. "Yes, I found it convin-

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cing. I think that working women should be helped by their husbands. I see a happy female character (YK2)". Again, one participant stated that men in Turkey do not behave in this way and did not find the plot of the advertisement realistic. "Frankly, I did not find it very convincing because we do not see something like this in Turkish men in general. I think all men should help their wives (YK2)". The fact that the male character was vacuuming while the female character sat down and continued her work was positively distinctive for the participants, but prejudiced statements were also made that men would not be skilled enough to do housework. "If a message is being sent through a man, it could be like this, it is not a job that men do much anyway. Sweeping the house was even more difficult with old-fashioned brooms. I saw him as a homebody, someone who likes to help his wife and is meticulous (YK3)". Participants belonging to Generation Y stated that they mostly do cooking, washing clothes and dishes, vacuuming and dusting at home, and emphasized that they do almost all household chores. A participant who continues to live with her family said that although she does all kinds of housework, there are days when she spends less time on these tasks; the mother, a member of Generation X in this household, undertakes these tasks. I tidy up and clean my own environment, my room. I do a lot of housework when I'm at home, but since I'm not at home very much, I can say that there are many periods when I don't do work at home (YK1)".

The views of men in the Y generation are summarized below:

Generation Y males generally find the advertisement impressive and convincing; they focus mostly on the transformation of the product from wired to wireless. "I found it convincing because it was nice that they kept up with technology (YE1)". "I found it convincing. It reflects that Arçelik keeps up with the changing technology. I found it convincing in this regard (YE3)". The effects used in the animation sections of the advertisement were appreciated by the participants and it was seen that these effects helped the product achieve its informative goal. "Yes, I found it interesting. Because the animation gives us clarity. It shows the ease of use of the broom (YE2)". The majority of the participants found the description of the features of the product sufficient but emphasized that the functions of the product should be covered in more detail and alter-

natively. "I found it remarkable, the change in the vacuum cleaner with technology was more striking. (YE1)", "Yes. The advertising design was sufficient (YE2)". The conversion of the product from wired to wireless was seen as a convenience by the participants, and some participants even stated that they could be more efficient in the elaborate sweeping work they do less. Some of the participants found it disturbing that the female character was passive/submissive in the advertisement but explained the reason for this disturbance as taking up unnecessary space in the advertisement. "There is nothing extra about the female character because she does not have a message (YE1)", "The part I do not like is that the role of the female character is ineffective and takes up space visually. I think this situation creates a decrease in the quality of the advertisement (YE2)". Participants who found the male actor in the advertisement appropriate were more interested in the functions of the product rather than the actors. Pointing out that it is a general belief in society that housework is perceived as something that belongs only to women, the participants said that men can also do housework. "Yes, I find it remarkable, because the subject of cleaning is generally associated with women, this cleaning advertisement made by a man is remarkable (YE3)", "There was not much of a message, but the fact that a man is vacuuming highlights the male character that has kept up with the modern age (YE1)". They stated that men prefer to stay away from this kind of work due to this general acceptance, and one participant even described this situation as "taboo". "The female character was effective in this respect; there is a taboo created by them that only women should do housework. The fact that the male character uses the vacuum cleaner while the woman is working on the computer in the corner breaks this taboo. In other words, I think the ad provides a balance (YE3)". Male participants belonging to Generation Y stated that they do more cooking, laundry and dishwashing, and daily minor cleaning at home, and less dusting and detailed vacuuming. One participant said that he liked the housework he did and found it entertaining. "I like to wash dishes and mop the floor. I also like to hang curtains because I am asked to help with this at home, and that pleases me. I also like washing dishes, it is very nice when accompanied by a song. I don't like vacuuming, but when I saw the product in this advertisement, I was attracted by its ease of use, so now I might like vacuuming (YE2)".

Table 2. Generation Y's Views on Advertising

Advertising Elements	ZK1	ZK2	ZK3	ZK4	ZE1	ZE2	ZE3	ZE4
Convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing	Convincing

Impressive	Not Impressive	Not Impressive	Not Impressive	Impressive	Impressive	Impressive	Not Impressive	Impressive
Interesting	Not Interesting	Interesting	Interesting	Not Interesting	Interesting	Not Interesting	Interesting	Interesting
Informative	Not Informative	Informative	Informative	Informative	Informative	Informative	Informative	Informative
Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable	Understandable
Attention Grabbing	Not Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing	Not Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing	Not Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing	Attention Grabbing
Message Relevance	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable	Suitable
Likability	Not Liked	Not Liked	Liked	Not Liked	Not Liked	Liked	Liked	Liked
The persuasiveness of the male character's message	Not convincing	Not convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Not convincing	Not convincing	Convincing
The persuasiveness of the female character's message	Convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Not convincing	Not Convincing	Convincing	Convincing	Convincing
Pleasant elements	Father-child figure	Nature and conservation	Family co-operation	Family co-operation	Cleanliness	Fast Cleaning	Family co-operation	Blue and green colors
Unpleasant elements	Splitting the family in two	Male characters remain in the background	Denigrating the rival company	Unrealistic	There is nothing unpleasant	Roles are unrealistic	There is nothing unpleasant	There is nothing unpleasant

The views of women in Generation Z are summarized below:

Although women in Generation Z did not find the advertisement convincing in general, they found it impressive that male and female characters wash dishes together. "I didn't find it convincing because I don't think any chemical can remove it without rubbing (ZK2)", "I found it impressive because it shows the sharing of work in the family" (ZK4). Participants who described the information in the advertisement as simple and ordinary stated that they found the advertisement understandable and appropriate. However, they also pointed out that it would not be possible to clean such heavy stains in the machine alone. "I found it informative because they expressed what they wanted to say in the advertisement (ZK2)", "I did not find it convincing because the whole family cannot wash one dish and I do not think that the dry stain will come out only in the machine" (ZK4). Despite the simplicity of the message, the use of visual effects was appreciated, and one participant stated that the use of the green theme for Fairy draws an image associated with saving and nature. The fact that family members work together in the

advertisement caused all participants to approach the advertisement positively, and some participants even said that they think that men, not women, should be more prominent in this advertisement. Stating that these messages could set an example for boys, one participant pointed out that the way male characters do housework should be covered in more detail in the advertisement. "I can't say I found it very impressive, but when I think about it, it is striking and eye-catching because the visual effects are used well (ZK3)", "It is shown that men also take part in housework. The fact that the boy also helps is a good example for the boys. It could have been just men instead of women. In a way that one man gives information to the other" (ZK4). One participant described the "Uğraşangiller" mother (name in the ad) who was busier with the dishes as more tired and the "Pratikgiller" mother (name in the ad) who did less work as more energetic; she predicted that the "Pratikgiller" mother would have more time for her family. "The woman who used the competitor's detergent was more tired and could spend less time with both housework and her family, but on the other hand, the woman who used Fairy Platinum see-

med to be more energetic because she did not have to exert any physical strength or power (ZK3).” Some participants were disturbed by the fact that the “Uğraşangiller” family, in which the mother does more work, is portrayed as if they are doing something very wrong, while the “Pratikgiller” family is positioned as a perfect family because the machine is not enough to remove those stains. “They divided the family into two families, as if it was a huge mistake... They put up a dishwashing detergent advertisement as if they were making one of the biggest mistakes. They also put up the family that used Fairy as if it was a perfect family. I didn’t like that very much, I can say that (ZK1)”. One participant emphasized that she felt “used” in both types of work, stating that she did all kinds of farming work, including lifting weights (which she considered to be a men’s job), and that she continued to do all household chores at home after this work. “I do the jobs that men do. I lift a lot of weights, and I can say that I play a leading role in housework. On top of working for hours, I also get up and do housework. I can say that I am used a lot in both jobs (ZK1)”. Other participants stated that they mostly do cleaning, vacuuming, and dishwashing, while they do less cooking. “I do a lot of cleaning work, I mostly deal with the dishes and less with cooking (ZK2)”, “I do my general cleaning, I usually vacuum a lot, since I don’t eat much at home and I usually vacuum more because I work (ZK3)”.

The views of men in Generation Z are summarized below:

Men in Generation Z generally found the ad convincing and found it impressive that male and female characters wash dishes together and in sharing. “I found it convincing. Because; the effects in this advertisement made by Fairy, the cleaning of the dishes, etc. made it very convincing (ZE1)”, “Yes. I liked it because there was cooperation within the family (ZE3)”. The participants, who found the information in the advertisement understandable, simple, and appropriate, described the delivery of the message through visual effects as remarkable. In particular, the comparison of the products and the dishwashing styles of the families was found impressive, especially the green and blue colors used in the advertisement attracted attention. “I think it was appropriate, as I said, there is a comparison. The colors were used beautifully, and based on this, there was a side that attracted human psychology. Therefore, I think the message was given (ZE3)”, “Those colors were used because the liveliness of the colors definitely touched on human psychology, and the cooperation within the family, that is, from the youngest to the oldest (ZE3)”. The fact that Fairy washes dirty plates by washing them directly in the machine without any scrubbing was considered interesting, but doubts were also expressed. “No. Because I use a

dishwasher myself and because of that I believe it is unrealistic (ZE3)”. The participants stated that the fact that the female characters in the role of mother were more prominent placed them in a guiding, decision-making position in terms of dishwashing, and they evaluated the male characters as passive/submissive. “So I didn’t like it very much because the male characters had no role and they just stood in the background (ZE2)”, “The women were more in the foreground, so no (ZE3)”. In general, the participants did not indicate any significant disturbing issue in the advertisement and were more focused on the functions of the product and visual effects. Two participants stated that they do less washing and placing dishes and more vacuuming and floor-sweeping. One of the participants stated that he did not do any housework, while another participant stated that he did all housework with pleasure. “I don’t do any housework at home (ZE2)”, “Everything from wiping doors to doing laundry, from cleaning the house to washing dishes. House cleaning in general. General cleaning of the house, in other words sweeping and mopping, I really like all of these. If I have to give a specific detail, I can’t because I love them all. Dusting in general (ZE3)”.

Discussion

Gender is shaped by being influenced by socio-cultural characteristics. Advertisements also play an important role in this shaping. In this study, advertisements of 3 different brands broadcast in Turkey were shown to generations X, Y and Z and their opinions were taken. In the Solo advertisement, men and women working together in the kitchen was evaluated as a positive example. The advertisement emphasizes men’s participation in cleaning work and lightening the burden of women. Participants also expressed that they would like to see women doing different jobs in advertisements. In the Arçelik advertisement, the male actor is positioned as “helping his wife” in vacuuming and is shown taking an active role in the house. The fact that the female character is passive while the male character does the housework in the advertisement was evaluated positively. The fact that family members work together in the Fairy advertisement caused all participants to have a positive approach. Some participants stated that male characters should be more prominent and that these messages could set an example for boys. They emphasized that the way male characters do their work should be covered in more detail, and criticized the fact that female characters were more prominent in dishwashing and that the work done by male characters was not shown sufficiently. Participants also emphasized that showing women not only cleaning but also doing different jobs in advertisements would contribute to the diversification of gender roles. In a similar study, it was revealed that

advertisements that portray women as strong and emphasize gender equality are more accepted and such advertisements are more effective (Başfıncı et al., 2018). It is seen that some of the female participants have prejudices that men do not have sufficient skills to do housework. While the majority of generations X, Y, and Z expressed a positive opinion about men and women doing housework together, they did not find the message given in the advertisement realistic. However, they found this message positive and wanted men's domestic work to continue and increase. They pointed out that giving this message in advertisements could change the perception of gender. Although stereotypes about gender roles continue in society (Eisend et al., 2019), the results in some advertisements show that gender perception has begun to change. For example, a study determined that there were positive developments regarding women's roles in advertisements, and that family roles and various roles emerged in male portrayals (Tsichla, 2020: 28). In a similar study, it was determined that the advertisements examined mostly contained traditional gender roles, but there were some progressive roles (Sanay & Şener, 2021). In a study conducted on 8 advertisements shot between 2020 and 2023, it was determined that the advertisements destroyed social preconceptions about the roles of men and women and treated the man as an individual who takes care of his children and home (Doğan & Kahraman, 2023). In advertisements published for March 8 International Women's Day, it was seen that women were portrayed outside of traditional gender roles (Çilingir, 2019). In this study and some academic studies, it is seen that stereotypes in gender perception, especially in advertisements, are now beginning to change.

Conclusion and Implications

In this study, the perceptions of generations X, Y, and Z in Turkey towards advertising campaigns that aim to transform gender stereotypes are revealed. Within the scope of the study, 24 people were interviewed and their opinions about gender were obtained through 3 advertisements belonging to different brands. As a result, it was evaluated positively that men, as well as women, were active and did work at home. Participants also demanded that women be portrayed in different work areas in advertisements. In addition, it was positively received that family members worked together at home in the advertisements that were shown. Participants also emphasized that showing women in advertisements doing different jobs, not just cleaning, would contribute to the diversification of gender roles. Finally, in line with the results of the research, various recommendations are presented. Advertising can contribute to the evolution of gender roles by promoting egalitarian approaches to housework.

Showing women not only cleaning but also doing different jobs in advertisements can contribute to the evolution of gender roles. Men taking an active role in housework in advertisements can help change social perceptions. Advertising messages that emphasize that housework is not a task that belongs to women can increase men's participation in these chores. Advertisements that show housework as enjoyable can help to create a more positive perception of these tasks. Normalizing men's active role in housework can be a positive step towards gender equality. Furthermore, in future studies, comparisons can be made with different countries by taking the opinions of different generations on the advertisements of different brands.

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